

FABRICATION OF ALUMINUM ALLOYS/CERAMIC PARTICULATES COMPOSITES BY MEANS OF A COMPOCASTING TECHNIQUE, MICROSTRUCTURE AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES.

C. García-Cordovilla^a, E. Louis^{a,b}, A. Pamies^a, A. Alonso^a y J. Narciso^a

a. Industria Española del Aluminio, Centro de Investigación y Desarrollo, Apartado 25, E-03080 Alicante, Spain.

b. Departamento de Física Aplicada, Universidad de Alicante, Apartado 99, E-03080 Alicante, Spain.

ABSTRACT

Aluminum alloys/ceramic particulates composites have been fabricated by means of a compocasting apparatus designed and set up in our laboratories. In particular, composites of Al-Si and Al-Mg-Si alloys/SiC particulates have been obtained. In this paper some of the most remarkable characteristics of the fabrication process are described. The microstructure and properties of the composites are also discussed. The distribution of particles in the as-cast material is rather uniform; extrusion increases this uniformity. The mechanical properties and the thermal expansion coefficient of the extruded material have been determined and compared with the results available in the literature. Fracture surfaces reveal that adhesion between the matrix and the particulates is satisfactory.

Keywords: aluminum alloys, SiC particulates, metal-matrix composites, compocasting.

1. INTRODUCTION

At the early stages of the development of Metal Matrix Composites (MMC), the major efforts were addressed to MMC with continuous reinforcements, since maximum strength is most easily attained with these materials [1-3]. However, continuously reinforced composites cannot be processed through standard metal working routes, and they have to be used in the as-fabricated shape. In addition they are highly anisotropic and very expensive. Thus, many companies turned

their attention to discontinuous MMC, reinforced either with whiskers or particulates. Among the fabrication processes that have been, or are being, developed to fabricate discontinuous MMC, one of the most productive and less expensive is molten metal mixing or compositing [3]. This technique allows, once mixing has been achieved, to fabricate standard semi-continuous Direct Chill (DC) ingots, that can be subsequently extruded, rolled or forged. Material fabricated through this process is now being commercialized by several firms [3].

During the last year a compositing apparatus has been designed, assembled and set up in our laboratories. This paper describes the fabrication of aluminium alloys/ceramic particulates by means of this apparatus. In particular composites of Al-Si and Al-Mg-Si alloys/SiC particulates have been obtained. In order to promote wetting and reduce the formation of aluminium carbide, the particles were oxidized at high temperatures prior to mixing [3-5]. Some of the salient features of the fabrication process are discussed. The microstructure and the mechanical properties of the fabricated composites have also been investigated, and the results compared with those reported in the literature.

2. COMPOCASTING APPARATUS AND FABRICATION PRACTICES

2.1. Compositing apparatus

Mixing was carried out in a pressure/vacuum chamber. It was made of steel, and has 36.4 cm of inner diameter and a wall 1.2 cm thick, whereas the bottom and the lid have a thickness of 2.0 cm. Imperviousness was achieved by means of a graphited spirometallic gasket. A resistance furnace was located inside the chamber. Vacuum was applied by means of a rotary pump that can reach 0.93 mbar. Actual pressures were measured by means of a sensor that works in the range 1×10^{-2} - 2×10^3 mbar. The dispersing impeller was designed so as to maximize mixing, while keeping the vortex at the liquid metal surface at a minimum. The design of the blades was optimized by carrying out several trials in oil/particles mixtures. A variable speed DC motor allows to rotate the impeller up to 3000 rpm.

2.2. Materials

The composites were fabricated using of three commercial Al-Si-Mg alloys (A-356, A-357 and AA6061) and SiC particulates of the green type (approximate purity 99.5%) and average

diameter of 27 μm . The particulates were heat treated in air at 1000°C for approximately 24h, to promote oxidation. This heat treatment is addressed to improve wetting and reduce the formation of aluminum carbide. The amount of particulates was varied in the range 8-18% vol. To facilitate the comparison of final properties, monolithic alloys were also obtained by the same route.

Figure 1. Typical microstructures of the composites fabricated in this work: a) defective mixing, A356-14% SiC_p, b) adequate mixing, A356-18% SiC_p, and, c) as b) for extruded material.

2.3. Fabrication practices

The alloys are melted in mullite crucibles of 200 mm internal diameter x 300 mm height, at a temperature around 50 °C above liquidus. The liquid metal is cleaned and degassed by bubbling argon through the melt. The pressure in the chamber and the temperature of the melt are registered during the whole process. All tools to be introduced in the liquid metal, the impeller included, are sprayed with a ceramic coating.

To avoid an excessive decrease of the liquid metal temperature, the particles and the impeller are pre-heated at 600 °C. Before the particles are added, the metal surface is cleaned to remove oxides. Then the mixing assembly is put in place, the chamber closed and the vacuum pump switched on. Only after the pressure goes below 100 mbar mixing starts; the mixing pressure is usually in the range 20-40 mbar. Several mixing stages are required to introduce all particles;

only a fraction of the total amount of particles is added at each stage. Once mixing has been satisfactorily obtained, the composite is cast by means of a suitable casting technique.

3. MICROSTRUCTURE AND PROPERTIES

3.1. Microstructure

The microstructure of the composites was investigated by means of optical microscopy and Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC). As shown in Fig. 1, adequate mixing leads to a rather uniform distribution of the particulates and a low porosity. The observable clustering of particles is of metallurgical origin. For instance during solidification there is a tendency to concentrate particles in the interdendritic spaces (Fig. 1b). These inhomogeneities are, however, nearly eliminated during hot working (Fig. 1c). On the other hand freezing conditions may also affect particle distribution, as illustrated in Fig. 2. At exceedingly high freezing rates the solidification front cannot engulf the particles, leading to particle-free regions as discussed in Refs. [6,7].

Figure 2. Microstructure of composite samples (A356-SiC_p - 15% vol.) taken from several zones of the same ingot, that were subjected to different cooling rates.

The DSC measurements were performed using a Perkin-Elmer DSC-2 apparatus. Runs were carried out at a heating rate of 20 K min⁻¹ from 320 to 875 K, and under a dynamic argon atmosphere (1 l/h). High purity aluminum was used as a reference. The composites and the

monolithic alloys were investigated in the as-quenched condition and after natural or artificial ageings. Here we shall only comment the results for the naturally aged condition (Fig. 3). Although the thermograms for the two alloys are significantly different, they show the same sequence of reactions: a weak endothermic peak related to the redissolution of GP zones, two exothermic peaks associated to β'' and β' formation, respectively, and, finally, several endothermic reactions related to the redissolution of all phases. In both thermograms it is noted that SiC particles accelerate the formation of the intermediate phases β'' and β' , as already observed by other authors [9,10]. This effect is much more important in AA6061. On the other hand, a sharp peak around 825 K in the thermogram of AA6061-SiC_p should be associated to low melting point eutectics involving Mg₂Si. The fact that this peak was not observed in the host alloy is consistent with the findings of Ref. [10] in the sense that the temperature required to fully solubilize the composite is higher than that commonly used for AA6061 alloy. Other differences between the monolithic alloy and the composite are less clear and deserve a more detailed study.

Figure 3. DSC thermograms for two of the alloys fabricated in this work in the naturally aged condition, with (continuous lines) and without (broken lines) SiC particulates (15% vol.).

3.2. Thermal expansion coefficient

The thermal expansion coefficient (α) was determined in a Perkin-Elmer Thermomechanical Analyzer. The measurements were performed at a heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹ from 50 to 480 °C, with a constant loading force of 100 mN, and under a dynamic nitrogen atmosphere (1.8 l/h). The results for α are reported in Table 1. As expected, the addition of particulates sharply decreases the thermal expansion coefficient. This reduction is larger in A357 (around 25%) than

in AA6061 (around 15%). We finally note that the experimental data for α are smaller than the results obtained from the rule of mixtures, as expected [11].

3.3. Mechanical properties

Tensile tests were performed in an Instron servohydraulic mechanical testing machine, fitted with a load cell of 5000 kg. Constant extension tests were made at a crosshead speed of 10 mm/min. Non-standard cylindrical samples of 5 mm in diameter were used. The results are summarized in Table 1. It is first noted that the addition of particles increases the Brinell hardness of A357 in a 10% and that of AA6061 in 20%. In both alloys the Young modulus (E) increases in around a 25%. The results for the Young modulus of alloy AA6061 are in excellent agreement with those reported in Ref. [8]. On the other hand, although the experimental data do not agree with the results obtained from the rule of mixtures, as expected for discontinuous composites [11], they are in very good agreement with those given by the Tsai-Halpin equation [11,12]. In fact, if we take an aspect ratio of 1 (reasonable for the particulates used in this work) and a Young's modulus of 440 GPa for the SiC particulates, the results for the Young's modulus of the composites based on A357 and AA6061, are 85 and 99 GPa respectively, in excellent agreement with the data reported in Table 1.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of the monolithic alloys and the composites fabricated in this work, in the T6 temper. The Ultimate Tensile Strength (UTS) and the Yield Stress (YS) are given in MPa, whereas the Young Modulus (E) is given in GPa. Results for the thermal expansion coefficient α (in $10^{-6} K^{-1}$) in the temperature range 50-480 °C, are also reported.

Alloy	UTS	YS	E	HB	α
A357	344	284	64	121	21.4
A357-SiC _p (15% vol.)	333	294	82	135	17.0
AA6061	374	363	76	124	23.5
AA6061-SiC _p (15% vol.)	396	379	98	148	19.5

The effect of particle additions on yield and ultimate tensile strengths (YS and UTS, respectively) is less important. In particular it is noted that the UTS of the reinforced A357 alloy is less than that of the monolithic material. This is surely a consequence of defects (for

instance porosity) that have a more pronounced effects on properties at fracture (UTS and elongation). In any case the increase in these two properties is always less than 6%. In this context, it should be pointed out that the temperature used to solution treat the AA6061 alloy may not be high enough for the composite, as discussed above and in Ref. [10]. We also note that our results for the YS and UTS of the monolithic AA6061 alloy are somewhat higher than those reported in Ref. [8].

3.4. Fracture surfaces

Fracture surfaces were examined by means of Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). Two typical micrographs are shown in Fig. 4. Fracture surfaces show the dimples characteristic of ductile fracture. The extensive cracking of the SiC particulates observed in the composites samples, demonstrate that high interfacial strengths are obtained in the composite.

Figure 4. Fracture surfaces of A356-SiC_p (9% vol.) material in the T6 temper.

This is further illustrated by the fact that many particles do not cleanly show up, but rather they are partially covered by the host metal. We have also observed (not shown in the figure) that cracking of particles is more important in peak-aged material (T6) than in T4 material, as expected.

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